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**“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”**

**“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”**

**«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
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- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
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- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of improving investment climate management. The role of the investment climate in promoting economic growth, strengthening investment activity, and increasing investment attractiveness is analyzed. The article also highlights the factors influencing the investment climate, modern mechanisms for its management, and key directions for improving investment policy. Based on the research results, scientific and practical proposals have been developed to enhance the efficiency of investment climate management, reduce investment risks, create favorable conditions for investors, and ensure the effective use of investment potential.

Keywords: investment climate, investment attractiveness, investment potential, investment policy, investment activity, investment risk, economic growth, investment efficiency, investment management, innovative development, business environment, investment infrastructure.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada investitsiya muhitini boshqarishni takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlarini tadqiq etilgan. Investitsiya muhitining iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash, investitsion faollikni oshirish va investitsion jozibadorlikni kuchaytirishdagi o'rnini tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, investitsiya muhitiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, uni boshqarishning zamonaviy mexanizmlari hamda investitsiya siyosatini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida investitsiya muhitini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish, investitsion xavflarni kamaytirish, investorlar uchun qulay sharoitlar yaratish va investitsiya salohiyatidan samarali foydalanishga qaratilgan ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: investitsiya muhiti, investitsion jozibadorlik, investitsiya salohiyati, investitsiya siyosati, investitsion faollik, investitsion xavf, iqtisodiy o'sish, investitsiya samaradorligi, investitsiyalarni boshqarish, innovatsion rivojlanish, biznes muhiti, investitsiya infratuzilmasi.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические аспекты совершенствования управления инвестиционным климатом. Проанализирована роль инвестиционного климата в обеспечении экономического роста, повышении инвестиционной активности и инвестиционной привлекательности. Также освещены факторы, влияющие на инвестиционный климат, современные механизмы его управления и направления совершенствования инвестиционной политики. По результатам исследования разработаны научно-практические предложения и рекомендации, направленные на повышение эффективности управления инвестиционным климатом, снижение инвестиционных рисков, создание благоприятных условий для инвесторов и эффективное использование инвестиционного потенциала.

Ключевые слова: инвестиционный климат, инвестиционная привлекательность, инвестиционный потенциал, инвестиционная политика, инвестиционная активность, инвестиционный риск, экономический рост, эффективность инвестиций, управление инвестициями, инновационное развитие, деловая среда, инвестиционная инфраструктура.

INTRODUCTION

The acceleration of globalization processes in the world economy, the expansion of international capital flows, and the intensification of competition for investment have further increased the relevance of effective investment climate management. A country's investment attractiveness is primarily determined by the quality

and stability of its investment climate, as well as the conditions created for investors. Therefore, managing and continuously improving the investment climate is one of the priority areas of economic policy.

In the current environment, the role of investment in ensuring sustainable economic growth, modernizing production, developing innovative activities, and creating new jobs is increasing. Attracting investment resources and ensuring their effective use largely depend on the state of the investment climate. A favorable investment climate stimulates the economic activity of investors, while existing challenges and limitations may reduce investment inflows.

Large-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to support investment activity, protect investors' rights, improve the business environment, and increase investment attractiveness. At the same time, there is a need to further improve investment climate management mechanisms, make effective use of investment opportunities across regions and sectors, reduce investment risks, and introduce modern management methods.

In this regard, scientific research on improving investment climate management, developing its theoretical and methodological foundations, and enhancing practical mechanisms is of great importance for modernizing the economy and ensuring long-term sustainable economic growth.

In a market economy, effective investment climate management is one of the key factors in ensuring economic development, increasing investment activity, and strengthening the competitiveness of economic sectors. The investment climate reflects a set of economic, legal, political, organizational, and social factors that influence investors in the process of making investment decisions. Therefore, the attractiveness and stability of the investment climate are among the main criteria determining the volume and efficiency of investment flows.

Today, the modernization of the economy, technological renewal of production, and acceleration of innovative development require further improvement of the investment climate management system. Increasing the efficiency of existing institutional mechanisms, protecting investors' rights, simplifying administrative procedures, and digitalizing public services are among the most important tasks in this area. In particular, reducing excessive administrative barriers in the implementation of investment projects can help increase investor activity.

One of the important directions for improving investment climate management is the further development of the regulatory framework. The stability, transparency, and compliance of investment legislation with international standards strengthen investor confidence. At the same time, creating equal conditions for participants in investment activity and ensuring the protection of property rights serve to increase investment attractiveness.

The importance of a regional approach in investment climate management is also increasing. It is necessary to implement a differentiated investment policy based on the economic potential, resource base, infrastructure capacity, and investment needs of each region. This approach allows for the effective use of investment resources, helps reduce economic disparities between regions, and supports the formation of new economic growth points.

In the context of the digital economy, the use of modern information and communication technologies is of great importance in investment climate management. Electronic monitoring of investment projects, the introduction of online communication systems with investors, the formation of investment databases, and the provision of services based on the "single window" principle ensure greater transparency and efficiency in investment processes.

Special attention should also be paid to the factor of innovative development in improving investment climate management. Supporting innovation activities, commercializing research results, financing startup projects, and developing high-tech production contribute to improving the qualitative composition of investments.

International experience shows that the effectiveness of the investment climate is closely related to the quality of public administration, the level of economic freedom, the development of infrastructure, and the favorable conditions created for investors. Therefore, in the process of improving investment climate management, the application of advanced foreign experience adapted to the specific characteristics of the national economy is of great importance.

In general, improving investment climate management is an important condition for ensuring sustainable economic growth, increasing investment attractiveness, creating new jobs, and strengthening the country's competitiveness in the international economic arena. Therefore, the continuous improvement of investment climate management mechanisms remains one of the priority areas of modern economic policy.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is worth noting that improving investment climate management is one of the key factors in ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy, increasing production capacity, and strengthening competitiveness in international markets. In modern economic conditions, attracting investment serves not

only to increase financial resources but also to introduce advanced technologies, innovative approaches, and modern management practices into various sectors of the economy.

The results of the study show that the attractiveness of the investment climate depends primarily on political and macroeconomic stability, the strength of legal guarantees, the protection of property rights, and the openness and transparency of public administration. Therefore, further improving the regulatory framework governing investment activity, reducing administrative barriers, simplifying tax and customs procedures, and creating a favorable business environment for investors remain among the priority tasks.

In addition, effective management of investment projects, regular monitoring of their performance, the widespread implementation of digital technologies, and the effective use of public-private partnership mechanisms will further improve the quality of the investment climate. International experience shows that favorable conditions created for investors increase the inflow of foreign direct investment, create new jobs, expand export potential, and improve the living standards of the population.

Thus, improving investment climate management is an important strategic direction of economic development. Its effective organization will serve to strengthen the country's long-term development, economic security, and position in the international investment arena.

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